

Assessment of DRL Testing Methodology for Autonomous Guidance in Space Applications

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Autonomy guidance is increasingly crucial in space missions due to several factors driving the exploration and utilization of space. At the same time, among Artificial Intelligence methods, Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) begins to play an important role in addressing the generalization challenges associated with different mission scenarios. The proposed work develops and proposes a process based on model selection, reward modelling, and initial condition randomness, to train and test DRL for autonomous guidance in space applications. Three different scenarios are used as case study and for the methodology development: debris collision avoidance strategy planning of LEO spacecraft, guidance optimization of the launcher's first stage landing, and robotic arm trajectory optimization for capture uncooperative targets.

1 Introduction

In the last few years, enhanced autonomy became the research driver of most of the leading space agencies, as spacecraft independence would increase the reliability, cost-effectiveness and flexibility of space missions. In the meanwhile, the number of works on machine learning techniques applied to space-related problems is growing [1–3], affecting almost all the most important aspects of the space missions in a great variety of scenarios ranging from feasibility studies to on-board applications. A branch of these applications focuses on automatize the guidance and control of different mission scenarios through deep reinforcement learning (DRL) [4, 5]. In this short paper, we want to focus attention towards the methodology used to train and test DRL on different space applications characterized by the same level of complexity in terms of environment conditions, state-action space and reward modelling. In the following, after a brief explanation on the developed approach, three different applications have been reported and investigated.

The proposed methodology is based on three main analyses that involve:

- **Model selection:** in terms of network architecture and state-action space definition.
- **Reward modelling:** which includes the selection of the complexity of the mission's objectives.
- **Initial conditions robustness:** where all the parameters involved in the random selection and their relative randomness level are defined or designed.

The adopted workflow based on these three aspects is schematized in Figure 1. This methodology is proposed as a sort of *vademecum* or guidelines to follow for the implementation and testing of a robust DRL-based path or strategy planning agent. Indeed, in the following section three different scenarios will be analysed underlying the benefit obtained by this workflow philosophy, whether fully or partially exploited.

From a superficial layer point of view, the rationale behind this structure comes from a very obvious functionality: testing the approach on a simpler and easier problem helps in understanding the initial performances of the approach and finding out which are the most important points to investigate more in-depth. As shown in Figure 1, the proposed workflow differentiates between two kinds of scenario definitions, characterized by two different levels of complexity. These levels can be shaped both by the definition of the model and by that of the reward function. The model depends on many factors and aspects, but, among all, is mainly described by the network architecture and the state-action spaces; on the other side, the reward formulation embeds the mission objectives. Once these two, or more if needed, cases have been selected, the workflow proposes to train and test them with different levels of initial conditions. This difference may be interpreted in two distinct ways: the first is related to the randomness level of the initial conditions, while the second to the selection of a simplified or realistic subset of them. In the end, what matters is that in one case, the state space possibilities are reduced with respect to the other. In Figure 1,

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the distinction between the methodology steps (1 to 4) and the *feedback* steps is highlighted by the different lines' colours: black and red. This wants to underline the adaptability of this *vademecum* which must face the need to tune the process without precluding any possibilities (in terms of model and reward) in defining them *a priori*.

Figure 1: Schematization of the proposed workflow methodology.

This kind of philosophy may not be strictly followed but instead should be adaptable case by case. The following three examples adopt this proposed philosophy, adjusting it in relation to their desired needs.

2 Space Applications Analysis

In the following subsections, the three different applications will be briefly analysed, focusing more on the approach methodology in terms of training and testing design. The first application regards the debris collision avoidance strategy planning of LEO spacecrafts; the second is related to the guidance optimization of the launcher's first stage landing; finally the third concerns again the guidance and control optimization of a robotic arm aimed to capture uncooperative targets.

2.1 Debris Collision Avoidance's Strategy Planning

The motivations behind this analysis are moved by the increase in the complexity of the safety problems to space operations, which are undermined by the great number of debris orbiting the Earth. Indeed, each week, hundreds of warnings on possible encounters with other spacecrafts or space objects are detected and issued for lots of LEO satellites in Conjunction Data Messages (CDMs), containing information on the time of closest approach, miss distance, relative position and velocity of the two objects, together with the time of last accepted observation. For this reason, leading space agencies are investing in the automation of collision avoidance processes; also exploiting machine learning tools [6–8]. Here, the analysis wants to investigate the applicability of DRL techniques to the design of sub-optimal long-term impulsive collision avoidance strategies [9].

Following the framework described in Figure 2, the analysis is shaped with a scenario based on the synthetic generation of space debris through the ESA's *Meteoroid and Space Debris Terrestrial Environment Reference* (MASTER-8), which considers the actual distribution of the conjunction events along one orbit, used to compute the collision avoidance probability [7]. The state model is differentiated into a simpler and a more complex space; concerning the action space, it is divided into two different discrete models: the simplest contains a set of five different impulses, corresponding to an altitude raised by multiples of 0.2 km and a no manoeuvrer option. The most complex model, instead, considers a set of three different impulses associated with an altitude increase or decrease by multiples of 0.3 km and a no manoeuvrer option. If the redundancy in the reward model has been sacrificed to benefit the variability of the state and action model, the complexity in the initial conditions divides two subsets of environments: one considering equatorial circular orbits and another considering sun-synchronous circular orbits. The methodology declination is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Collision avoidance scenario workflow scheme.

For an in-depth analysis of the results please refer to [9]. Anyway, from the summary of the results in Table 1, it is observable how the workflow is beneficial to the average performance, despite the increasing problem complexity.

Table 1: Results of A2C-based collision avoidance strategy optimization for LEO satellites.

Orbit	State	Action	Avg. Result	
LEO at 7129 km	Simple	Simple	Score	95
			Mass left	18 %
			Damage	16 %
LEO at 7129 km	Complex	Complex	Score	98
			Mass left	5 %
			Damage	10 %
SSO at 7078 km	Complex	Complex	Score	115
			Mass left	6 %
			Damage	5 %

2.2 Launcher’s First Stage Propulsive Landing

This second scenario is moved by the increasing importance of planetary landing problem, pushed by the growing technology of reusable launchers. This problem wants to optimize the achievement of a successful touchdown on a planet in terms of time, and fuel consumption, minimizing the terminal error within prescribed location bounds, velocity limits, and attitude constraints, through DRL, following the analysis of some recent works on DRL-based planetary landing focused on the lunar rendezvous and landing using image-based guidance through meta-learning [10] or different thruster configurations for extraterrestrial planetary related problems [11–13]. This case, performed in the framework of [14], aims to apply model-free reinforcement learning to achieve a successful atmospheric landing by directly controlling the launcher’s gimbaled thruster.

The problem is subdivided into two levels of complexity: at first, the rocket model is studied on a 3-dof basis defined in the inertial reference frame, under some peculiar assumption, i.e. atmospheric density constant, gravity field uniform, average inertia matrix, and axial aerodynamical force. The second level, instead, considers a full 6-dof scenario in which the translational and rotational dynamics are uncoupled. The architecture is based on a continuous state-action space, in which the state is defined by the rocket’s position and velocity, angular orientation and velocity; the action, instead, consists of a thrust vector and gimbal angles with limited feasible ranges. A two-step reward function has been defined for both the environments: at first, the reward targets an *heuristic* velocity [13], aiming for the landing state, in a second moment it focuses more on the optimization of the fuel consumption [12]. To complete the process, two sets of initial conditions have been used for the training anal-

ysis differentiating them by complexity: the first set is *simplified* to help with the tuning of the reward function; the second, instead, is derived from real rockets’ reentry historical data.

In Figure 3 the testing methods are schematized, partially reflecting the workflow proposed: the diversification of the reward model is sacrificed to benefit the analysis of different models and initial conditions, without burdening too much the entire analysis. All the combinations of these two aspects are, therefore, studied. For an in-depth overview of this case study, please refer to [14].

Figure 3: Launcher’s first stage landing scenario workflow scheme.

2.3 Robotic Capture of Uncooperative Targets

This last third scenario falls again in the context of In-Orbit Servicing (IOS) and Active Debris Removal (ADR), which, as already underlined, are operations of increasing interest, especially to guarantee the longevity of space endeavours and reduce the costs of the missions. Nevertheless, several strategies have been proposed to reduce the active debris problem (nets and tethered systems, etc. [15]), these approaches are suited for ADR but are not applicable to IOS; reason why, instead, the interest in robotic systems is strongly increased, even if these systems are more complex. To make up to this complexity, DRL may be used to enhance the guidance and control of robotic arms in space, helping to overcome problems such as the inverse kinematics for high-dof manipulators, collision avoidance and motion constraints [16–18]. The application briefly described here is extrapolated by the wider framework developed in [19], where, through the use of DRL, is wanted to train and test an autonomous agent to acquire the capability of carrying out the guidance tasks of a robotic manipulator, to synchronize the end-effector’s state (position + attitude) to grasp the uncooperative target, and finally reducing any relative motion.

The workflow defined in Figure 1 has been partially followed, in particular in terms of reward shaping and initial conditions analysis. The problem is based on a free-flying space robot, which is modelled as a multi-body system with a 6-dof controllable base and a 7-dof manipulator. The input state is composed of the current joint angles and rates, the errors between the

end-effector’s desired and current states, and the relative distances between the manipulator’s links and the target. The action space, instead, is discrete and it is defined by the desired joint rates of the manipulator, which are fed to the robotic arm controller, which is a simple tuned PD. Two different rewards models have been defined: the first only takes into consideration the position and attitude of the end-effector guidance to the desired state, and the minimization of the time taken by the end-effector to synchronize with the desired state; the second, instead, adds also the avoidance of a keep-out zone around the target. Different levels of initial conditions are defined in the analysis framework: the basic one features the fixed position of the centre of mass of the robot’s base along the target’s angular momentum vector. The second case of initial conditions, instead, is more complex: the initial manipulator configuration maintains the same level of randomness, but a further level is reached considering that the target spin velocity is randomized between a limited range, a random displacement is added to the robot’s base-target distance, and also the grasping position is extended to the whole face of the target.

Figure 4 sums up the aspects which may vary during the training and testing analysis of this case study.

Figure 4: Robotic arm grasping scenario workflow scheme.

In Table 2, the main results obtained during the analysis have been summarized. It can be noticed how the workflow philosophy has been followed differentiating between different reward models and initial conditions values.

Table 2: Robotic arm autonomous guidance results.

Reward	Objective	Init. Cond.	Success
Pos.+T.	GC	Basic	93.5%
Pos.+T.	Time	Basic	100%
Pos.+T.+CA	GC+CA	Basic	100%
Pos.+T.+CA	GC+CA	Dis.Rand	75%
Pos.+T.+CA	GC+CA	Grasp.Rand	47%
Pos.+T.+CA	GC+CA	Random	100%

3 Final Discussion

In Table 3, the three presented case studies are compared focusing on the methodology aspects. All of

them support the main analysis carried out throughout the methodology development, helping to tune the methodology itself. The first case, treating CAM strategy planning, helped strengthen the feasibility of reinforcement learning as a valuable tool for planning space mission-related problems. Afterwards, the second case backs up the choice of going more in-depth in the design of more complex state and action spaces, defining them more closely to a spacecraft’s realistic behaviour, while the last one pushes especially in the direction of understanding all the possible failures derived by a training activity which is inevitably unaware of all the aspects which may affect the knowledge of the environment. In the end, these analyses on different space environments and applications are judged helpful for the design of a training and testing process to investigate DRL for autonomous guidance and control in space missions. For this reason, the future research directions should be more focused on fixing the testing and training methodology, instead of just following emerging trends in DRL for space missions (i.e. such as scalability to larger mission scopes, integration with existing mission planning frameworks, or adaptation to unforeseen environmental conditions). Indeed, these novel DRL techniques have been positively studied and classified in different space applications which can be described as continuous state-action space. Instead, the novelty that this study tries to propose is to define a common strategy to analyse very different scenarios which, anyway, share the same definition scheme.

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Table 3: Case study scenarios comparison.

Scenario	Model Complexity	Reward Modelling	Init. Cond. Randomness
Debris Collision Avoidance Planning	The complexity is declined in terms of state and action spaces.	-	The IC analysis is subdivided in complexity and not by randomness.
First Stage Propulsive Landing	The complexity is declined in two different dynamics models: 3dof and 6dof.	-	Two subsets of random initial conditions are exploited and differentiated by complexity.
Robotic Capture	-	Two levels of reward models: basic and improved (more tasks are required).	Two subsets of initial conditions are exploited: fixed and random.

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